

Weapon Detection Using PTZ Cameras

Juan Daniel Muñoz¹[0009-0008-2484-4087], Jesus Ruiz-Santaquiteria¹[0000-0003-1454-7624], Oscar Deniz¹[0000-0002-0841-4131], and Gloria Bueno¹[0000-0002-7345-4869]

VISILAB, E.T.S. Ingeniería Industrial, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain
{juandaniel.munoz, jesus.ralegre, oscar.deniz, gloria.bueno}@uclm.es

Abstract. Massive shooting in public places are a stigma in some countries. Computer vision techniques are being actively researched in the last few years to process video from surveillance cameras and immediately detect the presence of an armed individual. The research, however, has focused on images taken from cameras that are (as is the typical case) far from the entrance where the individual first appears. However, most modern video surveillance cameras have some pan-tilt-zoom (PTZ) capabilities, fully controllable by the operator or some control software. In this paper, we make the first (as far as the authors know) exploration on the use of PTZ cameras in this particular problem. Our results unequivocally reveal the transformative impact of integrating PTZ functionality, particularly zoom and tracking capabilities, on the overall performance of these weapon detection models. Experiments were carefully executed in controlled environments, including laboratory and classroom settings, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation. In these settings, the utility of PTZ in improving detection outcomes became evident, especially when confronted with challenging conditions such as dim lighting or multiple individuals in the scene. This research underscores the immense potential of modern PTZ cameras for automatic firearm detection. This advancement holds the promise of augmenting public safety and security.

Keywords: CCTV video surveillance · Weapon detection · PTZ cameras · Object detection.

1 Introduction

Public safety and the prevention of criminal acts are fundamental concerns in our society. In this context, weapon detection has become a priority to ensure secure environments in both public and private spaces. Incidents of armed violence, such as mass shootings, armed robberies, and acts of terrorism, have increased in frequency and magnitude worldwide, leading to a growing demand for effective weapon detection technologies.

Early and accurate detection of weapons is essential for timely prevention and response to risk situations. Identifying individuals carrying firearms, knives, or other dangerous objects allows for immediate intervention, thereby minimizing potential harm or loss of human lives. Furthermore, weapon detection con-

tributes to deterring potential perpetrators and fosters a secure environment that promotes peace and people’s confidence.

Situations like the tragic shootings that have occurred in the United States (schools, shopping centers, etc.) could have been mitigated with early detection. The surveillance images captured in such cases show that it should be possible to detect the risk: the left image in Figure 1 was captured from a security camera during the shooting at Columbine High School; the right image was captured during the shooting at Covenant School in Nashville in 2023.

Fig. 1. Left image: security camera footage of the shooting incident at Columbine. Right image: security camera footage of the shooting incident at Covenant. Sources: [10], [7]

Computer vision research has considered the problem of automatically detecting an individual with a weapon. All of the published works, however, have considered images as taken from a static surveillance camera which is far from the individual. In such images the individual and the weapon appear with a small size and sometimes it is difficult even for human operators to discern both. While that is a realistic scenario, it misses on the opportunity of modern PTZ cameras. PTZ cameras have become more compact, and their cost has significantly dropped in the last years, making them a highly viable option when deploying CCTV surveillance systems.

In this paper, we make the first (as far as the authors know) exploration on the use of PTZ cameras in this particular problem of automatic weapon detection from a distance. Two CNN based on object (firearm) detection architectures were used: Faster R-CNN [15] and EfficientDet [17]. The objective of the study is to assess if PTZ capabilities allow for more efficient firearm detection.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews existing work on handgun detection using surveillance cameras. Section 3 describes the proposed method. The experiments carried out and the results obtained are summarized in Section 4. Finally, conclusions and future work are presented in Section 5.

2 Related Work

The detection of weapons has been a subject of intense research and development for several decades and has recently experienced significant advancements due to progress in computer vision and machine learning. Below, we provide a brief review of some articles that have addressed this topic.

In [1], an approach based on deep learning techniques is proposed for real-time weapon detection in CCTV videos. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are employed to extract discriminant features (shape and texture) and classify images as weapons or non-weapons.

In [16], automatic weapon detection in security systems is also proposed using deep learning techniques. This article describes a study based on three Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) applied to the automatic detection of weapons in images extracted from surveillance videos. The models take into consideration not only the discriminant features of potential weapons (shape and texture) but also the pose of the individual carrying the weapon. Thus, the model is provided not only with the (image of the) weapon itself but also with information about the body pose of the individual. As can be expected, this contributed to achieving improved results.

Other relevant studies can be discussed, such as [6]. In this research, the objective is to develop a real-time threat level detection system and the classification of targets (i.e. humans, vehicles, weapons) intended for use in border security. To detect and classify the targets, the authors used an object detector based on the classic Viola-Jones method[18].

With respect to PTZ cameras, in [11], an automated video surveillance system is designed. In that research, the proposed system detects anomalous objects with respect to the object type. The raw object detections are supplied by a convolutional neural network. The system does not need any manually labelled data, since a nonparametric probabilistic model of the object types normally found in the scene is learned in an unsupervised way. A kernel density estimator based on the Dirichlet distribution is proposed for this purpose. The probabilistic model yields an estimation of the probability that an object is anomalous. This information is passed on to a camera control module, which follows and focuses on the object (thanks to the PTZ camera movements, which allow accurate tracking) which is most likely to be anomalous in the current field of view.

In [3], PTZs are proposed for their usage in public places, private security, and military operations. The formal 'PTZ Search Problem' (PTZSP) is introduced, in which a stationary PTZ camera must navigate in a three-dimensional space to detect objects of interest. Rewards and penalties are assigned for each correct and incorrect detection, respectively, as well as for the time expended. The PTZSP is related to the Orienteering Problem with Functional Profits (OPFP) [12], but due to the vast search space, it is challenging to address with existing algorithms. The article proposed a series of simulations in large outdoor environments and various algorithms to solve the PTZSP.

In other works, such as [5], an approach based on background subtraction is proposed for the detection of moving objects in image sequences captured

with PTZ cameras. This approach introduces a neural network-based method where the background model adapts automatically and self-organizes to changes in the scene background. A series of experiments with real image sequences are conducted, demonstrating the effectiveness of the presented approach.

As mentioned above, there is no evidence of work where PTZ cameras are utilized for the automatic detection of weapons. The recent lines of research where the body pose and even hand pose (see the recent work [2]) are considered as additional cues show that there is potential for the use of PTZ capabilities in this problem.

3 Tracking/zoom system

Within the context of this research, the focus is directed towards the most pivotal component: the proposed method for tracking potential handguns. This method represents the cornerstone of our work, as it addresses the critical need for enhanced security measures and real-time threat detection. The method starts from a weapon detector that performs a first detection, which should then be confirmed or discarded thanks to the PTZ capabilities.

This system can be divided in the following steps:

1. Starting from an initial static camera position (Pan = 0.5; Tilt = 0.2; Zoom = 0.0), when a first detection occurs, the current Pan-Tilt-Zoom parameters are obtained, and the camera adjusts its Pan-Tilt to align the detection's bounding box with the center of the frame (with a certain tolerance). This is accomplished by comparing the center of the detection's bounding box with the center of the frame (with a resolution of 640x480 pixels in this case).
2. Once it is centered, a zooming procedure begins on the bounding box. Zoom is only applied when the bounding box is centered, meaning that even if zoom has already been applied, if there is any misalignment in the frame, the camera readjusts to the bounding box before continuing to zoom.
3. The zoom is applied based on the size of the bounding box relative to the frame. In other words, if the handgun is far away and a significant amount of zoom has been applied, and suddenly it starts getting closer, with excessive zoom, it would become indistinguishable. To ensure that the bounding box still fits within the frame and the handgun remains visible, the zoom is reduced. This is achieved by dynamically modifying the zoom value at any time depending on the current zoom value.
4. Furthermore, in addition to this, when the camera starts detecting and initiates tracking, if there is no further detection within 3 seconds from the last one, the camera returns to its initial position in search for a new detection.

To convert the horizontal and vertical distances between the centers of the bounding box and the frame into Pan and Tilt distances (both Pan and Tilt typically have values ranging from 0 to 1) the distances are linearly scaled to values between 0 and 1, which are then passed to a function that moves the camera in Pan and Tilt as necessary. The camera's adjustment also depends

on the zoom applied at any given moment, as higher zoom requires smaller adjustments. Expression 1 is used to transform values relative to the frame into values ranging from 0 to 1. The expression provided is for Pan, and a similar approach is applied to Tilt. It is important to note that if the target value is outside these ranges, the camera moves to the minimum or maximum values accordingly.

$$npp = pp + [a - b] \cdot (c - zp) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$a = \frac{dx - dminp}{dmaxp - dminp} \cdot (nmax - nmin) + nmin \quad (2)$$

$$b = \frac{ref - dminp}{dmaxp - dminp} \cdot (nmax - nmin) \quad (3)$$

The variables in Expressions 1, 2, 3 are defined as:

- **npp** : the target Pan setting.
- **pp**: the current Pan.
- **dx** : the difference in the x-axis between the center of the frame and the center of the bounding box.
- **dminp** : equal to $\frac{-\text{frame width}}{2}$, which represents the maximum negative horizontal distance between the center of the frame and the center of the bounding box.
- **dmaxp** : equal to $\frac{\text{frame width}}{2}$, which represents the maximum positive horizontal distance between the center of the frame and the center of the bounding box.
- **nmax** : the maximum value in the new range, which is 1.
- **nmin** : the minimum value in the new range, which is 0.
- **ref** : the reference value in the original range [dminp, dmaxp], which is 0.
- **c** : a constant obtained based on the current zoom.
- **zp** : the current zoom value.

4 Experiments

This section provides an overview of the experimental setup and methodology employed in this study. Prior to delving into the specifics, a brief summary of the objectives is presented. Our objective is to compare the effect of PTZ in this problem, with respect to the use of a static non-PTZ camera. Thus, in our case we capture the same scene using two PTZ cameras: one static and the other effectively utilizing the PTZ movements. To ensure uniform conditions. Note that two identical PTZ cameras have been employed to use the same type of sensor and ensure identical conditions. The static camera covers a larger field of view, while the PTZ-enabled camera will adjust and zoom in on any detected handguns.

4.1 Experimental setup

The cameras used are HIKVISION IP PTZ cameras (HiWatch Series, specifically the model HWP-N2204IH-DE3 [8]). They are positioned side by side, securely mounted on a wooden base (covered with black vinyl) on a tripod to ensure that the captured images are nearly identical (see Figures 2, 3).

Fig. 2. Assembly of PTZ cameras. Left image: position for recording experiments. Right image: attachment of the base.

Fig. 3. Assembly of PTZ cameras. Left image: front view. Right image: rear view (Ethernet cable power connection).

In the experiments, both cameras record video and start the recording at the same time. Firstly, they move to a position of 0.5 in pan (midpoint) and 0.2 in tilt, with the zoom set to 0 (a range between 0 and 1 has been chosen for these values, using the ONVIF protocol). Meanwhile, the camera that applies the real-time model adjusts its PTZ values based on detections, while the other camera remains static. Furthermore, if the PTZ has already moved from the initial position due to a first handgun detection and then no further detection is obtained 3 seconds (a user-selected value), it returns to its original position to reevaluate the area.

Of all the possible bounding boxes detected within the same frame, we only take the one with the highest score returned by the model. We retain a single detection per frame, as we evaluate a realistic situation in which, normally, at most, only one gun appears in the scene.

From the generated videos, the bounding box information for each frame is exported to JSON files, which are then compared with their corresponding ground truth annotations (based on Intersection over Union, IoU). By comparing the JSON files (which follow the COCO format in this case), results are obtained.

A wide range of situations has been studied (variations in clothes, lighting conditions, handgun positions, movements, recording angles, etc.) to demonstrate the aforementioned points.

4.2 Model Training

In order to analyze these situations and demonstrate the main objective, it is necessary to train the handgun detection architectures mentioned above (Faster R-CNN and EfficientDet), which are representative of existing work on the subject.

- **Faster R-CNN**: the implementation used for this architecture is available in the Torchvision library [14]. The ResNet101 backbone pretrained on ImageNet [4] was used.
- **EfficientDet**: the implementation used for this architecture is available at [19]. In this case, the “tf efficientnetv2 l” architecture was used as the backbone, also with pretrained parameters from ImageNet.

The dataset used for the training of both models was the pistol dataset created by the University of Granada in a seminal work [13]. The dataset split is summarized in Table 1. Note that there is only one class in this dataset, which is “Handgun”.

The selected values for the main hyperparameters are included in Table 2.

4.3 Results

The behavior of the system is studied in various scenarios. The following points outline the cases studied and their corresponding results. This allows for a final comparison between models and situations. In this case, an IoU threshold of 0.2

Table 1. The table displays the number of images from the dataset designated for training, validation, and testing of the detectors. The dataset comprises a total of 3000 images.

Train	Validation	Test	All
2160	240	600	3000

Table 2. Hyperparameters selected for the training of the detectors. The number of epochs is the number of times the model is trained on the entire dataset; the batch size indicates the number of training examples used in each weight update step during training; the learning rate is a value that determines how much the model’s weights should be adjusted in each training step. It controls the rate at which the model learns; the optimizer is an algorithm that adjusts the model’s weights during training to minimize the loss function.

	Faster R-CNN	EfficientDet
Number of epochs	50	50
Batch size	4	8
Learning rate	0.001	0.001
Optimizer	SGD	AdamW

has been selected to obtain the results. It is an appropriate value in this case because the ground truth bounding boxes are much smaller than those generated by the model. This means that, although both bounding boxes highlight the handgun, with a relatively high IoU threshold, it is not considered a true positive (even though it is) due to the size difference in the bounding boxes (see Figure 4).

The metrics used for performance assessment are: *Precision*, or ratio of correctly detected objects over all positive predictions of a certain class, *Recall*, or ratio of correctly detected objects over all ground truth objects of a certain class, and *F1-score*, defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. In the result tables, only F1-score values (0 to 1 range) are shown.

Different situations were recorded in two locations: a laboratory and a classroom. Also, we studied: variations in clothes, lighting conditions, handgun positions, movements, recording angles, etc. It is important to mention that both cameras, the static PTZ (referred to as the static camera hereafter) and the PTZ camera that applies its characteristics movements (referred to as the PTZ camera hereafter), have been configured in the same way and they apply the model in the same way as well. The only difference between both cameras is that one applies tracking/zoom while the other one remains internally static.

Fig. 4. The image illustrates how Intersection over Union (IoU) is calculated. It is a commonly used evaluation metric in object detection tasks, as it measures the degree of overlap between two bounding boxes. Three cases with different overlaps are shown. As seen in the first case, even though the same object is being identified, the difference in size between the bounding boxes results in a low IoU, potentially leading to a false negative. This is why a small IoU threshold has been chosen. Source: [9].

Results with Faster R-CNN It is important to mention that when applying the model, a confidence threshold of 0.8 was chosen. This means that the model only considers bounding boxes with a score equal to or higher than 0.8, which was selected to mitigate false positives. Additionally, the videos recorded with this model have an average of approximately 150 frames (about 15 seconds of recording at around 10 FPS).

The results obtained with this detector in the laboratory are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Results obtained with the Faster R-CNN detector in the laboratory. Various scenarios have been studied, such as how the individual carries the handgun (aggressive aiming or calmly, lowered, without aiming at anyone), variations in lighting conditions at the location, among others. Two columns show the F1-score values obtained for both PTZ and static cameras.

Situation	F1-score	F1-score
	PTZ camera	Static camera
Lights on and person moving away	0.64	0.40
Lights on and person approaching from a distance, then moving away	0.60	0.51
Lights on and person with a handgun down	0.72	0.12
Lights off and person approaching from a distance, then moving away	0.55	0.28
Lights off and person moving away	0.81	0.28

Figure 5 shows an example of the situations analyzed. In this case, a person moves farther away from the camera. Two captures from the PTZ camera’s

recorded video are shown. In the left image of the figure, there is an initial detection (the bounding box of the detection is a green rectangle) while the camera is in its initial position. In the right frame, it can be seen how the camera has adjusted to the bounding box of the detection and zoomed in, providing a better view of the handgun. This zoom-in helps with subsequent detections.

Fig. 5. The scenario involves the lights turned on, and a person moving away from the camera in a laboratory setting. In the left frame, the handgun is detected, and in the right frame the camera adjusts to the bounding box of the detection through Pan-Tilt-Zoom movements. **PTZ** camera. **Faster R-CNN** model.

If we now view the video generated from applying the model to the static camera and extract the same time moments as those shown in Figure 5, we obtain the frames in Figure 6. Comparing Figures 5 and 6, both show detections. However, when looking at the right frames of both figures, the PTZ camera detects the “Handgun”, whereas the second one does not. This demonstrates how centering the bounding box and applying zoom contribute to a higher number of detections.

Moving onto the other location, the classroom, the results obtained are shown in Table 4.

One of the studied situations in the classroom is shown in Figure 7, where there are multiple individuals in the scenery: one with a mobile phone and another with a handgun. Zoom is particularly useful in such cases because it helps to eliminate false positives such as mobile phones (see the top two frames of the figure).

The model applied to the recording from the static camera performs significantly worse, as evident from the obtained results. Since it does not focus on the handgun, it gives fewer detections and is subject to a higher number of false positives (see the bottom frame of Figure 7).

Results with EfficientDet When applying this network, a confidence threshold of 0.55 was chosen. This means that the model only considers bounding

Fig. 6. Scenario with lights on and a person moving away from the camera. Location: laboratory. In the left frame, the handgun is detected, while in the right frame it is not detected because the camera does not apply zoom, and the person moves too far away. **Static** camera. **Faster R-CNN** model.

Fig. 7. Scenario with lights on and multiple people in the scene. Location: classroom. In the top left frame (**PTZ** camera), an initial detection is performed on a possible “Handgun”. In the top right frame (**PTZ** camera), a significant zoom has been applied to the handgun, reducing false positives. In the bottom frame (**static** camera), a mobile phone is detected as a handgun (false positive). **Faster R-CNN** model.

Table 4. Results obtained with the Faster R-CNN detector in the classroom. Various scenarios have been studied, such as the presence of two individuals in the scene, variations in clothes, among others. Two columns show the F1-score values obtained for both PTZ and static cameras.

Situation	F1-score	F1-score
	PTZ camera	Static camera
Lights off and person moving around the scene	0.62	0.52
Lights off and person moving around the scene (2)	0.63	0.41
Lights off and person moving away	0.80	0.43
Lights on and multiple people in the scene	0.76	0.28
Lights on, handgun down, and multiple people	0.86	0.31

boxes with a score equal to or higher than 0.55. This model is not as good as the Faster R-CNN taking into account the obtained metrics. However, our goal is to demonstrate the improvement in the detection rate through the Pan-Tilt-Zoom movements of the camera, even if the model is not performing as good as in the previous case. Videos were recorded in the same locations, but fewer in number since many different cases have already been studied with the Faster R-CNN model. Additionally, the videos recorded with this model have an average of approximately 255 frames (about 15 seconds of recording at around 17 FPS).

Results obtained in the laboratory are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Results obtained with the EfficientDet detector in the laboratory. Only a situation has been studied, as all of them have been studied with the other detector. Two columns show the F1-score values obtained for both PTZ and static cameras.

Situation	F1-score	F1-score
	PTZ camera	Static camera
Lights on and person moving away	0.81	0.13

Results with this architecture in the classroom scenario are shown in Table 6.

As shown in Figure 8, zoom is crucial and the detector works better when PTZ movements are applied

Table 6. Results obtained with the Efficient detector in the classroom scenario. Various conditions have been studied, such as variations in clothes or in lightning, among others. Two columns show the F1-score values obtained for both PTZ and static cameras.

Situation	F1-score PTZ camera	F1-score Static camera
Lights on and person moving around the scene	0.35	0.10
Lights on and person moving away	0.23	0.13
Lights on and person moving away (2)	0.46	0.27
Lights off and person moving away	0.61	0.03

Fig. 8. Scenario with lights off and a person moving away from the camera. Location: classroom. In the left frame (**PTZ** camera), the handgun is detected after previous detections and zoom application. In the right frame (**static** camera), no detection occurs. **EfficientDet** model.

5 Conclusions and future work

Overall, the results show that the use of PTZ capabilities through the implementation of tracking code significantly improves the performance of deep learning models in this problem, as seen in the results tables (much better results when PTZ is employed). E.g., in the case of Faster R-CNN, it is evident that using zoom and tracking is especially important when the handgun is down (see Table 3).

It is worth highlighting that, similar to when the handgun is down, the use of zoom and tracking of the “Handgun” in the situation of multiple people in the scene is crucial. This helps to avoid many false positives (see F1-score values in Table 4).

Comparing models, Faster R-CNN generally provides better results. This is because, as mentioned earlier, EfficientDet does not detect that well in this particular case. A possible solution to this would be lowering the IoU threshold for EfficientDet. However, this could lead to an increment of false negatives,

which is undesirable. Also, the architecture could be retrained in order to detect better, but the training of the neural networks is not critical in this study, as the intention is to demonstrate the improvement of the networks when using PTZ capabilities, rather than emphasizing the quality of the models in detection, as seen, e.g., in Table 5. Also, looking at Table 6, when the person moves away from the camera with the lights off, the usage of the tracking/zoom system is clearly significant.

It can be concluded that the objective that motivated the completion of this work has been successfully achieved, demonstrating that the use of PTZ cameras with a tracking/zoom system in the field of video surveillance, and more specifically in handgun detection, provides a significant improvement.

The implemented tracking system presents some limitations, such as locking onto a false positive, preventing it from detecting real handguns. This could be addressed by having the camera return to its initial position after a certain amount of time once tracking has started or, in situations with multiple potential handguns with high confidence, by tracking/zooming to cover all of them. Related to this, it would be interesting to explore scenarios with multiple detections instead of just one, as done in this work (the single detection assumption was made considering a lone shooter, as mentioned earlier). Also, achieving precise tracking/zoom in situations with very rapid movements that could cause the handgun to go out of frame, especially after applying a significant amount of zoom, is essential. Optimizing architectures with the TensorRT library could be considered to increase FPS performance, enabling the camera to react more quickly and make adjustments more frequently. Finally, we could point its ineffectiveness in distant situations initially, as it is necessary for the handgun to be close enough to the camera for an initial detection to occur. Only then can tracking/zoom be initiated, which will be effective in distant situations thereafter.

Future work shall also consider experiments with weapons other than handguns and scenes with multiple handguns.

As demonstrated, there are still many aspects to improve, but this initial exploration has shown that this system indeed offers more advantages than disadvantages.

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